

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVED DEFORMATION AND INCREASED HARDNESS IN AUTOMOTIVE ALLOY WITH THE ADDITION OF BISMUTH

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Abstract

This work developed a study on the modifications in aluminum alloy as such a development to apply to car body commercial of sedan vehicle, the results showed superior results in hardness, a integration of material in the alloy, a displacement on the peaks of profile obtained by X-Ray Diffraction and increased the displacement to be subjected the specimen to load in tensile test. Its knowledge can be used to develop of different news proposal of alloys in specific cases to use the capacity of deformation. The results showed values increased in the same direction than others works published in literature.

Keywords: Automotive alloys; Addition of bismuth; Aluminum alloy; Mechanical Strength; Hardness in alloys.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In recent years in automotive industry different material used in car body and space industries has been of increasing interest in various directions such as cost, energy saving, weight loss and strength. [Hirsch 1997]. Other interest has been developed strict legal requirements for environmental protection and increased crashworthiness [Tisza 2018]. Today there are different materials used in the automotive manufacture as conventional HSSs and AHSSs, composites in specific carbon fiber reinforced plastics or CFRP, advanced materials and alloys in aluminum series, magnesium, titanium. The new materials in automotive industry too are required to meet the fuel economy in terms of pollution emissions per kilometer drive and get a better performance in the characteristics of vehicles, one advantage is the average on fuel economy is also challenging every year, for example in the United States of America was reported by Wen Zhang, Jun Xu (2022). In this direction the lightweight composite materials are an emerging technology that had gathered much interest from the space and automotive industries (Siengchin, 2023). The results in less weight are oriented to get as 2025 goal of average CO₂ emissions to 89 g/km, reduced by about 40% compared with the last decade and the applications are extensively diverse in components such as dashboard, bumper, engine, transmission system, body shell, wheel, suspension system, brake, steering system, battery, seat, gearbox and accessories (Zhang y Xu, 2022). In automotive industry the addition of materials to develop new systems light and energy absorber are sectioned to new proposal in body car, it is necessary in the automotive market to offer advantages over other products in automotive market (Wang & Weiler, 2022). Is disponible a vision shows by Phaedra Martin (2025). She wrote that there are intense changes in the automotive industry, it will be in the next few years, oriented to be known more broadly

as “the mobility industry—the next generation of products and services” with transportation combined with new advantages in materials, digital sciences, and business models such as ride-sharing and shared ownership. The research improvement that products and services.

Materials such as aluminum and magnesium in alloys still in the context of their utilization in the metallurgical and automotive industry, it studies carried out in the literature help to solve the problem of reducing the weight of automotive devices and structures to reduce fuel consumption through the use of aluminum-magnesium alloys (Hao et al, 2023), while in the manufacture industry are use alloys with sufficient strength for stability and durability, good formability for stretching, joining like welding, high corrosion resistance and recyclability, there are series as 5xxx, 2xxx, 6xxx using Cu, Mg, Si and Zn in different series (Hirsch, 1997) (Zhang & Xu, 2022),

Studies on addition of materials in alloys are identified in diverse literature on recent years (Kılınc et al., 2023) (Hassan et al., 2020). The development of solder alloys still having interest on the research field, so the properties of an alloy significantly influence its utility and lifespan (Shenggang, 2023), there are materials added to alloys to get different mechanical properties and the addition of elements has demonstrated a certain composition, the progress of corrosion poses potential risks to personal safety degree of improvement in alloy properties, indicating the positive effect of elements such as Bi on the mechanical properties, the literature shows that studies have shown that the addition of Bi to alloy affects the electrochemical performance of the alloy to a certain extent, with limited research in this area, a particular research of alloys with different Bi contents (x = 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 15 wt%) were prepared by Shenggang et al., getting decreased properties in some cases while in others cases the corrosion resistance increased, the studies are limited to alloys with Sn and Cu.

Really the alloys used in body car are limited in their ability to make themselves known, it develop interest to try to identify the elements of alloys and explore the addition of bismuth, the commercial alloys with the mentioned material is not widely identified in the literature, it is a good possibility to the evaluation to commercial alloy used in vehicle to get the analysis of the results. We studied an alloy used in sedan vehicle, it was evaluated and compared with other alloy addition of bismuth oxide to show the results obtained.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used in alloy were obtained from door post in a compact commercial sedan vehicle. The addition of bismuth oxide particles from Sigma-Aldrich, with a purity of 99%, was carried out at a rate of 4% by weight. A Bruker D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer with 1.6 kW and Cu radiation ($\lambda = 0.14051 \text{ \AA}$) was used for structural characterization. The measurement was evaluated over a range of 15 to 80 degrees with a

step size of 0.02° . A LynxEye XE detector was used. Hardness was measured on a Mitutoyo WIZARD using a 15N scale. The photography from surface was obtained with a Scanning Electronic Microscope JOEL model JSM- 6000 in high vacuum with 10 kV. The deformation and mechanic strength measurements were obtained from Marxtex machine model ETM-100 with capacity in 100KN and velocity at 0.5 millimeter/minutes. Muffle furnace used was Felisa FE 340.

The procedure followed was to prepare samples, the first one was evaluated the original material after applying heat treatment below the melting temperature of aluminum, while in the second case bismuth oxide was added, the same heat treatment was applied as in the first case and then the samples were evaluated. The standard applied to sample was the ASTM E8/E8M, it standard shows the dimensions of the sample, the distances to fix the gage.

Table 1

Identification of samples	
Identification	Sample
A0	Original part aluminum alloy
A1	Alloy modified with bismuth

3.0 RESULTS

The alloys were evaluated with specimens in accordance with standard E8/E8M. The specimens A0 and A1 were subjected to heat treatment in different

time, in order to compare the results under the same conditions. The figure 1 shows the specimen inside of muffle furnace.

Figure 1. Specimen in muffle.

Within the results obtained after adding bismuth oxide it is possible to observe in the X-Ray Diffraction profile the phases present derived from the incorporation of bismuth, which is possible to appreciate in the phases identified in the profile A1 in figure 2, where the response profile at angles 32.2° , 45.2° and 45.4° could

be corresponds to the phases of $\text{Bi}_6\text{MoO}_{12}$ (PDF00-0036-0116) and 32° and 32.5° in $\text{Bi}_{0.9}\text{Al}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.9}\text{O}_3$ (PDF 01-081-8320), with the indexation it is possible to observe the integration of bismuth in the alloy structures and with this are attributed the changes in the properties.

Figure 3 Profiles from alloys A0 and A1.

In figure 3 the profiles are compared more closed, and the bismuth generate displacements on the peaks and were identified peaks of bismuth compounds (PDF 05-001-0353).

Figure 3. Displacement of peaks in profile of XRD

After to structural characterization with X-Ray Diffraction, the specimens were subjected to the same treatment conditions and were evaluated with respect to hardness under room temperature conditions, with the results shown in Table 2, the addition of bismuth increased the hardness by 32.25%.

Table 2.

Sample	Hardness (Scale 15N)
A0	15.5
A1	20.5

A technique used was the scanning electron microscopy in which it was possible to observe the modifications on the surface of the sample, situation origi-

nated by the thermal treatment and the addition of bismuth oxide on the sample A1, in figure 4 is an image clear on surface of specimen A0, while in figure 5 a layer was observed which is congruent with the results

of X-ray diffraction with the present a surface with particles.

Figure 4. Surface from alloy A0

Figure 5 Surface from alloy A1

Regarding the mechanical strength of the specimens when subjected to a tensile test under ASTM E8/8M standards, their stress-strain graphs were obtained. Figure 6 shows the graph corresponding to spec-

imen A0 and the results of specimen A1. Displacements in the deformation may be related to the change of crystal structure that may be generating point defects.

Figure 6. Mechanical strength in alloys

The modifications in alloy with addition of bismuth are in accordance with the study developed by Medine Kılınç et al. (2023), the hardness increased, new phases were identified. Obviously, the composition of alloy was different but generate new phases by the addition of the material with the results obtained by TEM and SEM. In other case in alloy of aluminum with addition of bismuth in 4% in weight was founded a very significant improvement beyond the 10.0% elongation observed from the control specimen, the value is lower than the results obtained in the present work but the results are in the same direction (Ugochukwu et al., 2024). The displacement observed in the

CONCLUSIONS

The addition of bismuth in alloy let identify the changes on the properties in the material. In the case of applications to automotive car body the mechanical resistance decrease, but the displacement increases in considerable value, it could help to use energy in deformation got values on 32% over the results obtained in original specimen, the profiles of X-Ray Diffraction showed the new phases with bismuth alloy in accordance with the 4% in weight, while the photographs from Scanning Electronic Microscope allow identify the material added and the modifications in surface.

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